

Air Pollution Management APM
Mattilamäki 38, 33610 Tampere

Version: TEAS 2019 (Version 1.0)
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File: C:\APM\TEAS modelings\GearBox.teas

JOB INFORMATION

Job: GearBox TiO₂ exposure potential assessment
Description: Underlying data for "Nanosized titanium dioxide particle emission potential from a commercial indoor air purifier photocatalytic surface – A case study"
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Notes:

Shift Length: 1440 minutes
Note1:

SUBSTANCE INFORMATION

Substance1:
Substance2:
CAS Number:
MW: g/Mole
SG: g/mL
VP: mmHg (Torr) at 20 C
BP: C
Notes:

EXPOSURE LIMITS

	Type	Source	Notes
OEL1: 0.3 ug/m ³		NIOSH REL	

TASK INFORMATION

TASK 1 - New Task
Description:
Model: M101
Model Name: 1Box.CE.Gv
Comments:

Variable	Variable Model	Units
1: Frequency	~ ConstantInt (1, ,)	/shift
2: Duration	~ ConstantInt (1440, ,)	min
3: G	~ Constant (0.01, ,)	ng/min
4: Q	~ Constant (0.1666, ,)	m ³ /min
5: V	~ Constant (20, ,)	m ³
6: tg	~ Constant (1440, ,)	min

Comments:

TWA CALCULATION (TASK OR FULL SHIFT)

Task TWA - the TWA is calculated for the duration of the task(s).

Comments:

SIMULATION OPTIONS

Unless noted below, for all variables modeled with a statistical distribution a random value was generated for each repeat of a task.

STATISTICS

Simulation N: 1

Output Units: ng/m³

Predicted value: 0.055 ng/m³ (during first 480 minutes)

GRAPHS
